

Psammobates tentorius trimeni
Namaqualand tent tortoise

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

Group: Reptile

Size: maximum 13 cm

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Distribution:

This species occurs exclusively on the west coast of South Africa, found only within the Succulent Karoo Biome, one of the world's recognised biodiversity hotspots.

Importance:

The Namaqualand tent tortoise is a vibrant and highly polymorphic seed disperser. Widely regarded as the most colourful tortoise in the world, it has a more restricted range than other tent tortoise species. Listed as "Near Threatened" by the IUCN, it faces pressures from habitat loss, the illegal pet trade, and increasing aridity. No genomic studies have been conducted on any tortoise species in Africa or the Southern Hemisphere.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 47.2 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 6.32 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 2.2 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.3% [Single: 95.3%, Duplicated: 2.3%]

Assembly N50: 450.04 kilobases

Contig number: 16 117

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Date Published: 2025-07-23

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16355317